

Deliverable 3.9

Implementation of New Funding Calls

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1. Executive Summary

New and Revised Approaches to Research Funding (ORION subtask 3.2.1) sought to integrate RRI principles in funding processes, co-creating funding calls with multiple stakeholders, thus 'opening-up' research funding.

Research funding organisations that participated in this ORION task, the *Instituto de Salud Carlos III* in Spain and the South Moravian Centre for International Mobility (JCMM) in Czech Republic, organised and led workshops with multiple stakeholders. Their co-creation experiments resulted in two complementary approaches: The RRI Health Awards (ISCIII) and a funding call for undergraduate research projects to address local societal challenges (JCMM).

The implementation of this task at ISCIII has succeeded in making the organisation more permeable for internal collaboration, displaying best practices on how to overcome typical challenges in hierarchical research funding organisations. The impact of the task at the institutional level has been acknowledging the RRI principles in the 2019 Accreditation Guide for ISCIII-funded Health Research Institutes, a milestone that ISCIII Director, Raquel Yotti, highlighted in the foreword in the annual memory. In the case of JCMM, their facilitation and coordination of ten Open Science research projects has elevated the organisation as an Open Science authority in the Czech Republic.

At the time of writing this report, both ISCIII and JCMM foresaw a reiteration of their open science approaches in the future, supported with local funds and institutional project management resources. A replication of ORION fostered approaches would provide an undisputable proof of impact of this ORION task at the institutional level. ISCIII has planned an evaluation of the impact of the first edition in the first quarter of 2021 before progressing with the second edition of the awards. The COVID-19 pandemic severely affected JCMM, with part of its core funding being cut, and the initiative there has been put on halt until further notice.

2. Call Background

The goal of this sub-task (3.2.1) of the ORION Open Science project is to develop new and revised approaches to research funding. The two research funding organizations partners in the ORION project, the Spanish *Instituto de Salud Carlos III* (ISCIII) for biomedical research and the Czech South Moravian Centre for International Mobility (JCMM), collaborated and took complementary approaches to explore integration of RRI and Open Science principles in funding processes, co-creating funding calls and prizes with multiple stakeholders, thus ‘opening-up’ research funding.

ISCIII co-created the ‘RRI Health Awards’¹ to recognise, encourage, promote and disseminate best practice examples on RRI aspects developed by ISCIII-accredited Health Research Institutes in 2019. There are 31 Health Research Institutes across the Spanish territory, gathering more than 162 institutions and encompassing over 24,000 researchers. Three awards of 10.000 € each were finally awarded.

The Health Research Institutes are clusters performing research and innovation in Biomedicine, Science and Technology, coordinated by ISCIII. These institutes are entities dedicated to basic and applied research that involve hospitals of the National Health System, universities, public research organisations and public or private research centers, have a multidisciplinary composition and involve many different stakeholders. The annual accreditation process seeks to ensure high standards in areas as ethics, gender equality, open access and transparency.

JCMM co-created a funding call for research projects to address local societal challenges for Master and PhD students at the 6 universities in Brno. With this funding call, JCMM sought to provide an opportunity for students to become more engaged with Open Science. Ten research projects were funded to be conducted during May 2019 until January 2020.

The co-creation aspect of the calls is explained in ORION deliverable 3.5. Depicted below is an overview of the timeline and development of this task by the two partaking funding organisations.

¹ <http://eu-isciii.es/premios-rri/> (last accessed 3rd November 2020)

3. Implementation of funders' complementary approaches

National Institute of Health Carlos III, Madrid, Spain, (ISCIII)

Timeline

Outputs

a. Official pre-announcement

The official pre-announcement of the call for the RRI Health Awards took place during one of the ISCIII National Forums, a biannual meeting with all the 31 Health Research Institutes. Attended by all institutes' Directors and Scientific Directors, this meeting is one of the most important appointments at the national level for these organisations. The National Forum serves to report on progress, share news and discuss concerns and ways of working with ISCIII.

PREMIOS EN INVESTIGACIÓN E INNOVACIÓN RESPONSABLE (RRI) EN SALUD

ORION open science
 MINISTERIO DE CIENCIA, INNOVACIÓN Y UNIVERSIDADES
 Instituto de Salud Carlos III

 OBJETIVO RECONOCER, PROMOVER Y APOYAR EL TRABAJO DE LOS IIS PARA INCORPORAR LOS PRINCIPIOS DE RRI	 CANDIDATOS TODOS AQUELLOS IIS ACREDITADOS POR EL ISCIII	 PREMIOS LOS PREMIOS ESTÁN DOTADOS CON UN FONDO TOTAL DE 30.000€ A REPARTIR ENTRE LOS PREMIADOS	 PLAZOS DEL 2 AL 20 DE ENERO 2020
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Más información IRIS SAN PEDRO
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RRI Health Award description presented during National Forum

During the National Forum on 20th November 2019, there was a session about the RRI Health Awards funded by ORION. In this session, ISCIII Deputy Director General, Gonzalo Arévalo, made a presentation to underline the key messages of the Awards, which were provided as a handout for participants. He then introduced ISCIII Project Manager for the RRI Health Awards, Iris San Pedro, encouraged submissions and gave time for questions.

The National Forum took place in the ISCIII Auditorium Ernest Lluch. The attendance was over one hundred people, including representatives of the Health Research Institutes and ISCIII representatives.

b. RRI Health Award Call (Brief Description)

The ISCIII, as coordinator of the network of Health Research Institutes, designed these awards to recognise and reward projects and activities aligned with the RRI principles developed by these institutions during 2019. Recognising and disseminating these projects and activities would contribute to raise awareness about RRI practices in health research and encourage broader uptake.

The awards were regulated by the EU Financial Regulation (art. 206 and art. 207), which contains the specific provisions for prizes, as well as the H2020 Participation Rules (art. 50).

The call basis² invited proposals on each of the following categories corresponding to the RRI principles:

- Ethics
- Gender equality
- Governance
- Open access
- Public engagement
- Scientific education

The call was open to all accredited Health Research Institutes and their staff, with the extent and degree of participation in the development of the presented RRI action deemed appropriate (whole Institute, research area/groups, interdepartmental multidisciplinary groups, with citizen participation, etc.). The applicant for each proposal had to be the legal representative of the relevant institute and each institute could submit a maximum of three proposals. All proposals submitted within the submission window that followed the submission process continued to the evaluation process.

RRI Health Award Flyer

c. Submission Process and Submitted Proposals

Process

ISCIII provided participants their institutional platform, Says, to prepare and submit the proposals. Says is a software all these institutions frequently use, which removed potential technological barriers. The use of Says guaranteed the safety and good use of the protocols and data. Overall, this platform made the whole process simpler and more effective.

The following supporting documents were developed to facilitate the submission process:

Call documents describing the awards and its scope:

- Guide for Applicants³ with the instructions for the application process
- FAQs⁴
- Template of the project report

² http://eu-isciii.es/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Bases_premios_RRI_salud_ISCIII.pdf (last accessed 5th November 2020)

³ https://www.orion-openscience.eu/public/2019-12/Guia_instrucciones_premios_RRI.pdf (last accessed 5th November 2020)

⁴ https://www.orion-openscience.eu/public/2019-12/FAQ-RRR_v1.0.pdf (last accessed 5th November 2020)

A valid submission had to include:

- An application form, with descriptive data on the project and its participants, as well as a list of the submitted documentation.
- A project report (template) , which would gather information about the carried out initiative, in a structured way to allow its evaluation. A memory format is available in the application form to facilitate its completion. Explanatory documents of the activity could be included as annexes, at the discretion of the applicants, and the link to the descriptive video had to be attached.
- Annex of the proposal with any relevant information. This annex had to be an assembled pdf with all the relevant documents.
- A video about the activity carried out in the project. A template for introduction was available in the platform.

The applicant for each proposal had to be the legal representative of the relevant Institute. Each Institute could submit a maximum of three proposals for these awards.

The submission period was from the 2nd January until 20 January 2020, 15:00 h (GMT+1).

Submitted Proposals

The following table and figures summarise the submitted proposals in terms of participation at scientific and territorial levels, gender balance of proponents, and the relative success of the RRI categories:

1. 26 proposals were submitted for this edition (figure 1). Three Institutes (one in the Bask country, Biocruces Bizkaia, and two in Barcelona, IMIM and IDIBAPS) submitted the maximum number of proposals; two institutes in Madrid (H.C San Carlos and H. de la Princesa) submitted two proposals.
2. 18 Health Research Institutes (58%) participated in the call (figure 2).
3. The participating institutes were widely spread over all the regions of Spain, with a representation of 70 % of the territories (figure 3).
4. Science Education and Public Engagement were the two RRI categories with more submitted proposals (figure 4). It was possible to participate in multiple categories at the same time.
5. Women, either in a role of Institute Managers or Project Managers (figure 5), submitted 42 % of proposals (figure 5).

Table with the list of proposals with links to the proposals' videos:

TITLE	HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE	LINK TO VIDEO
IDlescape: participa y descubre el proceso de la investigación en salud a través de un "escape room"	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA DE BELLVITGE (IDIBELL)	https://youtu.be/TN1VBfOsY2U
Proyecto de co-creación y participación ciudadana en el diseño del estudio PENSA de prevención de deterioro cognitivo en personas con quejas subjetivas de memoria	INSTITUTO HOSPITAL DEL MAR DE INVESTIGACIONES MEDICAS (IMIM)	https://youtu.be/kc7wKX60xrs
Sociedad e investigación, juntos de la mano por un envejecimiento saludable	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION SANITARIA BIODONOSTIA	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Hxb_Lrp_a1yJmBfYBvynvvMDrcfNhLMI
Rompiendo las barreras entre la investigación científica y los usuarios en salud mental.	INSTITUTO HOSPITAL DEL MAR DE INVESTIGACIONES MEDICAS (IMIM)	https://youtu.be/1hDwxV61BzQ
Nuevos escenarios para la ciencia ciudadana en salud: la escuela de primaria	INSTITUTO HOSPITAL DEL MAR DE INVESTIGACIONES MEDICAS (IMIM)	https://youtu.be/frcbl528jB8
Gestión e impacto en resultados: Evaluación de las acciones de gestión en un Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria	FUNDACION INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA HOSPITAL CLINICO SAN CARLOS	https://youtu.be/qgDo2xOF9qo
Participación ciudadana en la mejora de los servicios asistenciales- Espacio de Intercambio de experiencias	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACIONES BIOMEDICAS AUGUST PI I SUNYER (IDIBAPS)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3PL2ak3CCI0&feature=youtu.be
Talento femenino: Las científicas hablan	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACIONES BIOMEDICAS AUGUST PI I SUNYER (IDIBAPS)	https://youtu.be/NymDN5Rg2OQ
Ciencia abierta para todos	FUNDACION INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION SANITARIA ILLES BALEARS	https://youtu.be/2zZCStTgYWo
La Fábrica Princesa , los jóvenes como motor de RRI sanitaria en el IIS Princesa	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO DE LA PRINCESA	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7tungaVtpqI&feature=youtu.be
Comunicación audiovisual y redes sociales para potenciar la RRI, alianza IIS Princesa - Zinkinn	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO DE LA PRINCESA	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6TQJuSjdAM&feature=youtu.be
" Women in Science": Un grupo de trabajo para la promoción del cambio científico e institucional en igualdad de género en el Campus Can Ruti	FUNDACION INSTITUTO INV GERMANS TRIAS I PUJOL	https://youtu.be/coGHgQ2JzS0
Lo que realmente importa	INSTITUTO MAIMONIDES DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA DE CORDOBA (IMIBIC)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nzlelUbXKDI&t=1s
IdISSC: un espacio de investigación e innovación responsable como unidad de cultura científica	FUNDACION INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA HOSPITAL CLINICO SAN CARLOS	https://youtu.be/yjrDe8o-6zM
www.clinicbarcelona.org Información que te cuida	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACIONES BIOMEDICAS AUGUST PI I SUNYER (IDIBAPS)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oJ1SOMMSgHA&feature=youtu.be

TITLE	HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE	LINK TO VIDEO
El bus de la Salud, un proyecto pionero en prevención cardiovascular y renal	INSTITUTO INV. BIOMEDICA DE LLEIDA. FUNDACION DR. PIFARRE (IRBLLEIDA)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j85rtlFxuG0&feature=youtu.be
III Jornadas IBIMA-Farmaindustria. 'Acercando la ciencia a las escuelas. Investigación y desarrollo de medicamentos'	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA DE MALAGA (IBIMA)	https://youtu.be/ccmC1WN3Q-U
Modelo de teleasistencia centrado en el paciente	HOSPITAL MARQUES DE VALDECILLA	https://youtu.be/cq9aVAxM0FY
FAIR4Health: Hacia una aplicación responsable de los principios FAIR en la investigación en salud	HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO VIRGEN DEL ROCIO	https://youtu.be/B6KyrjdMbug
Estudio exploratorio del impacto de la investigación en la práctica asistencial en el Hospital Universitario Vall d'Hebron.	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO VALLE DE HEBRON (VHIR)	https://youtu.be/N5d8kGvWs4M
Proyecto interno participativo para evaluar la situación con relación a la igualdad de género y oportunidades y plantear acciones para avanzar en la igualdad y para difundir/fomentar la investigación y la ciencia en las/los jóvenes y hacia sociedad	BIOCRUCES HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE (IIS BIOCRUCES)	https://youtu.be/U-RZMMOJ90c
Los niños y sus familias: la voz que mejora el proceso del trasplante infantil	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO LA PAZ (IdiPAZ)	https://youtu.be/juBB2QHRQKM
Promoviendo la Conducta Responsable en Investigación: Desarrollo de las políticas de Integridad Científica en el IIS-FJD	FUNDACION INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION SANITARIA FUNDACION JIMENEZ DIAZ	https://youtu.be/xiLoRLZq79s
Descubrir tu pasión lo cambia todo	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACION BIOMEDICA DE SALAMANCA (IBSAL)	https://youtu.be/HsH4g5ir7WY
Iniciativas de educación y concienciación social sobre la investigación del cáncer infantil promovidas por el IIS Biocruces Bizkaia	BIOCRUCES HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE (IIS BIOCRUCES)	https://youtu.be/xlt8dyq19-!
Colaboración social integrada en proyectos de investigación en cáncer infantil	BIOCRUCES HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE (IIS BIOCRUCES)	https://youtu.be/56bcPR0oZ9I

Figure 1. Number of proposals submitted by HRI.

Legend: HRI=Health Research Institute; IBIDEL=Bellvitge Biomedical Research Institute; IDIVAL=Health Research Institute of Valdecilla Hospital; IMIM=Hospital del Mar Medical Research Institute; IBIMA=Malaga Biomedical Research Institute; FISEVI=Healthcare research management foundation of Andalucía; IDIBAPS=August Pi i Sunyer Biomedical Research Institute; IRBLLEIDA= Lleida Biomedical Research Institute

Figure 2. Participation rate

Figure 3. Regions participation rate

Figure 4. Proposals by RRI category*

Figure 5. Gender balance proponents

* Proposals could classify in more than one RRI category

d. Evaluation Process

Phase 1: Peer Review evaluation

All submitted proposals met the selection criteria outlined in the bases; therefore, all of them were accepted and continued to the evaluation phase.

The proposals underwent first a peer review. ISCIII composed a list of RRI experts choosing these experts from the National Contact Points network and in collaboration with other funding agencies, such as *Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología* (FECYT) and The Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (CDTI). The objective of this list was to bring together a group of experts for all RRI categories, at the national and international level. A territorial diversity in the origin of the RRI experts was also taken into account. 16 candidates were chosen for this list.

Based on the number of proposals to evaluate, the CV of the prospective evaluators and their availability, ten evaluators were selected from this list of RRI experts. They were divided in junior and senior, based on their experience and according to their possibilities of participation (such as in the case of Eva Méndez). The senior evaluators were responsible for the evaluation of the successful proposals selected by junior evaluators.

The junior evaluators' members were:

- Francisco Lara, Associate Professor in Ethics at Granada University.
- Ana Belén Cristóbal, Co-director in Greco European Open Science project.
- Eva Méndez, Open Science Evaluator at the European Commission.
- Jonathan Gómez-Raja, Scientific Coordinator at Extremadura Health Research Foundation.

The senior evaluator's members were:

- Michela Bertero, Head of International & Scientific Affairs, Centre for Genomic Regulations (Barcelona)
- Rosina Malagrida, Manager of Living Lab Health, IrsiCaixa
- Belén Jiménez, Director of I+I, Andalusian Foundation to Progress and Health
- Pastora Samper, Head of International Initiatives, Catalanian Open University (UOC)
- Itziar de Lecuona, Deputy Director, Bioethics Observatory
- Pilar Rico, Unity Chief in Open Access, Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)

The 26 proposals were first organised according to the proposal RRI category. They were then assigned to the evaluators matching their expertise in those categories. For example, the ethics proposals (4 proposals) were assigned to junior evaluator Francisco Lara, designated as an ethics expert, and Itziar Lecuona, Senior evaluator expert in ethics.

In the case of the group of senior evaluators, a smaller group in number, the workload was greater for most of the evaluators. However, the group of synthesis evaluators was able to spread the workload more. In all cases, we wanted the evaluator to feel as comfortable as possible with their work, and we even made last minute adjustments due to the workload of some evaluator caused by COVID.

The peer review was done online, using an online institutional platform, called Evays. This platform provided the evaluators access to the all documentation for their assigned proposals. This allowed a flexible process for evaluators while safeguarding data management.

Phase 2: Jury

ISCIII appointed a jury of experts⁵ in a selection process based on their knowledge and experience in RRI, and experience in evaluating and managing European projects. The composition of the Jury ensured a broad knowledge on the proposals' categories. The Jury members were the same as the senior evaluators.

The Jury assessed the proposals based on the call's terms. The Jury discussed their assessments during two online meetings, the first one on 22nd April and the second and final meeting on 8th May. The consensus reached during this last meeting was conclusive and determined the winners of this call.

e. Announcement of the Winners

The Jury decided to award the three prizes to the following proposals:

⁵ http://eu-isciii.es/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Miembros-Jurado_web.pdf (last accessed 5th November 2020)

Original Title: “Proyecto de co-Creación y Participación Ciudadana en el Diseño del Estudio PENSA de Prevención de Deterioro Cognitivo en Personas con Quejas Subjetivas de Memoria”.

English Title: "Project of co-Creation and Public Engagement in the Design of the PENSA Study of Prevention of Cognitive Impairment in People with Subjective Memory Complaints"

Institute: Instituto Hospital del Mar de Investigaciones Médicas (IMIM)

File number: RRI20/005

Description: This action, developed at the research group level, stands out for its application of citizen participation in the design of a clinical trial. This introduction of citizen participation once the study has begun, provides great value, since it allows the reorientation of the project, facilitating that it better adapt to the needs and expectations of the participants.

Original Title: “Lo que realmente importa”

English Title: “What really matters”

Institute: Instituto de Investigación Biomédica de Córdoba (IMIBIC)

File number: RRI20/018.

Description: This action has contributed with interesting elements in the area of scientific education for the development of the work carried out in and with the territory; and because of the novel approach in the methodology of inclusion of the different agents involved, with special emphasis on a fundamental axis, such as the generation of interest in science among the youth population. All of this makes this action a commendable attempt at education, well executed, which wisely directs its efforts to a key group.

Original Title: “Promoviendo la Conducta Responsable en Investigación: Desarrollo de las políticas de Integridad Científica en el IIS-FJD”

English Title: "Promoting Responsible Research: Development of Scientific Integrity Policies in the IIS-FJD"

Institute: Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria Fundación Jiménez Díaz (IIS-FJD).

File number: RRI20/028.

Description: This action has stood out for its contribution in the area of ethics and scientific integrity, for offering an adequate and useful implementation of the regulatory frameworks necessary for their application from the most institutional level. Through a methodologically robust design and with a development of great practical application, it focuses on this core, basic aspect, but not for that reason simple in its development. The action poses a well-planned regulatory framework rooted in the institutional structure, skilfully overcoming the difficulties that arise when proposing actions of this type. This action is an example of how to carry out an active policy of scientific integrity in the institutional framework.

ISCIID Director notified the award-winning candidates on 17th June and the signatories were required to give their express acceptance as required by institutional protocol. Following the express acceptance of each of the winning candidates, ISCIID announced the winners on 23th July.

The official notification to the winners was made by e-mail. ISCIII Director General, Raquel Yotti, sent the official notification letters to the three successful Health Research Institutes on 17th June 2020. The acceptance letters from arrived shortly after.

The acceptance ceremony took place online on 23rd July 2020. ISCIII Director, the prize-winners and ISCIII staff in charge of this ORION task attended the ceremony. During the ceremony, the compilation video of the winning proposals was shown, (see next section) and the awardees received a diploma acknowledging their participation and success in ORION ISCIII 'RRI Health Award'.

RRI Health Prizes Winners

f. Video of Winning Proposals

An Open Science project must have good dissemination elements. To align the 'RRI Health Award' with this characteristic of open science, ISCIII paid special attention throughout all the steps of the project to obtain simple, accessible, attractive and easy to disseminate materials.

Videos and images bring content closer to the public and are the most shared elements in social media networks. Accordingly, ISCIII included in the submission process a requirement for a one-minute video for each proposal. The videos were requested for promotion and dissemination purposes, with the ambition of increasing their reach and recognition in society. With these valuable materials, ISCIII commissioned an audio-visual provider to make a video of the three successful proposals.

To make the compilation video stimulating, useful and inspiring ISCIII requested the following elements to be included in the script:

- Inspiring presentation of RRI and OS and ORION project
- A brief explanation of the RRI Health Award
- Description of the prize-winners
- Testimonies of the winners, from the institutional and researcher point of view, explaining what it meant for them to have been awarded with this award

The video was made in a close collaboration between ISCIII and VA, ORION Communication Work Package Leader. Together they defined the video's structure and this collaboration was an active and fundamental part in the graphic design. The collaboration with the three winning

institutes was also very important. They provided the raw videos and the winners' testimonials.

A national and international dissemination campaign was coordinated between ISCIII and VA in close collaboration with the communication departments of the Institutes involved. These departments carried out the dissemination at the institutional level via its website and social networks.

The video is available in ISCIII YouTube channel⁶ (Spanish version) and ORION YouTube channel⁷ (English subtitles).

Some figures about the video engagement are:

- Over 700 combined views in the official YouTube channels of ISCIII and the winner institutions (IMIM, IMIBIC, IIS-FJD).
- Over 500 views in ISCIII LinkedIn profile: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/instituto-de-salud-carlos-iii_isciii-noticiasisciii-investigaciaejn-activity-6692390003877666816-lls5
- Over 3.000 combined views in the Facebook pages of ISCIII and the winner institutions.
- Over 8.200 views in ISCIII Twitter profile: <https://twitter.com/SaludISCIII/status/1286247969868718080>

Outcomes

Health Research Institute accreditation guide to include RRI principles

The most important institutional change at ISCIII has been to implement the RRI principles in the Health Research Institute Accreditation Guide. This is a great recognition of RRI practices, which also involves and encourage these practices.

The National Institute of Health Carlos III is, today more than ever, a benchmark institution in the field of health research. At this time of crisis caused by COVID 19, the organization is the national benchmark institution for health, forming part of the crisis management committee organized by the government. Its work focuses both on scientific advices on health (epidemiology, tests, and clinical processes) and on technical management as a laboratory (tests for the detection of COVID 19).

In this context, the National Institute of Health Carlos III, as RFPO, grants a quality accreditation to specific institutions (Health Research Institutes recognized by ISCIII) dedicated to biomedical research.

The Research Institutes are one of the main networks in biomedical research in Spain. All of them have their fundamental base in Spanish public hospitals, and in turn, generate alliances with primary care centers, universities, other public research institutions, health institutions, public and private foundations, etc.

⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=viVmua-j8vg&list=PLzDfYimVlaCnxKfb2YE_zUtHrPX8iHMXJ (last accessed 5th November 2020)

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oCU2kxsgfuU> (last accessed 5th November 2020)

Altogether, there are 31 Health Research institutes, gathering 162 institutions and more than 24,000 researchers. These Health Research institutes undergo an evaluation process that audits compliance with the criteria of the approved and current Technical Evaluation Guide. All the process is carried out as established by Spanish law (RD 279/2016 of June 24), on Accreditation of Institutes of Biomedical or Health Research. This Technical Evaluation Guide can therefore be considered the key document that turns any research institute into an ISCIII's recognized Health Research Institute.

One of the main outcomes for this ORION task at ISCIII has been achieving that the 2019 Technical Evaluation Guide for ISCIII Health Research institutes to be aligned with RRI principles. The guide now acknowledges the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation and Open Science, milestone that is highlighted in the Directors' foreword in ISCIII annual report⁸.

Two circumstances converged in this milestone. On the one hand, the desire of ISCIII to align itself with EU research policies, which implies the implementation of the RRI principles. On the other hand, ISCIII participation in the ORION project, which provided support and impetus to the RRI movement within ISCIII thereby propelling this institutional change.

Below, we offer a series of data and specific examples of how the guide aligns with RRI principles:

1. The RRI principles have been considered in the three sections defined by the guide (Governance; Strategy, capacities and performance; and Impact).
2. The guide has more than 150 subsections to consider, with 53 related to RRI principles. Therefore, 35% of the guide is dedicated to the RRI.
3. The Open Science Policy has a specific section. It defines a policy of open access for all the Health Research Institutes publications, and implements FAIR policies on the data.
4. There is a cross-cutting application of the principles of gender equality, both with regard to the constitution of the bodies of the Health Research institutes (scientific management, internal-external scientific committees) and to the human resources policy (equitable recruitment, policies of work-life balance).

Increased institutional porosity (intra-institutional collaboration)

Internally, these awards have given ISCIII the opportunity to collaboratively work together with two different departments: the Evaluation and Financing Department (SGEFI) and the International Department (SGPIIRI), making the institution a more porous and open organization. This collaboration between departments has allowed the implementation of the RRI not only in the Accreditation Guide but also in the workflow of the Institution.

ISCIII is supportive of organising a future reiteration of the RRI Awards. However, ISCIII will first conduct an evaluation of the current edition during the first quarter of 2021 to analyse changes produced in the Health Research Institutes facilitated by these awards.

⁸ <http://gesdoc.isciii.es/gesdoccontroller?action=download&id=04/11/2020-1740f1a296> (last accessed 5th November 2020)

Timeline

15/11/2018	Call Announcement (open for period of 2 months)
15/1/2019	Deadline of the Call
16 – 31/1/2019	Eligibility check
1 – 28/2/2019	Public peer review – <i>Authorea</i> web page
1 – 31/3/2019	Evaluation of the submitted projects by external evaluators
15/04/2019	Announcement of the winners of the competition
05/2019 – 01/2020	Individual projects carried out by students
03/2020	Conferences on the results of the work package, presentation of individual projects
04/2020	ORION task overview at JCMM annual meeting

Outputs

a. Research Projects

The individual students' projects started on the 1st of May 2019, with an expected total duration of 9 months/each.

The ten research projects were:

1. The Neural Correlates of Emotion Regulation, Masaryk University
2. The role of p53 in neural differentiation, Masaryk University
3. In vitro respiratory toxicity models RESPIROM, Masaryk University
4. Modelling Alzheimer's disease in the dish, Masaryk University
5. Open access to calcium phosphate scaffolds technology for regenerative medicine, Brno University of Technology
6. Efficacy of different bovine footbath disinfectants at various temperatures, Mendel University in Brno
7. 3D models with bio-origin, Brno University of Technology
8. Pure Water for Brno – Influence of controlled flushing of the water supply network on stability of the drinking water quality, Brno University of Technology
9. Pollution entering the Moravian Karst via surface streams, Brno University of Technology
10. Let's clean South Moravia from heavy metals: genomic variation in heavy metal hyper accumulating plant species *Noccaea caerulescens*, Masaryk University

At the end of September 2019, the grant holders submitted a short interim report, based on JCMM template, summarizing progress to date. All projects were finished by 31st January 2020 and final reports submitted to JCMM by 29th February 2020.

b. Round table to share research projects' results

On 9th March 2020, JCMM organised a final roundtable at their premises. The 10 grant-holders of Masaryk University, Brno University of Technology and Mendel University presented their results and projects, which were carried out over the period of 9 months. Interestingly, the projects ranged from medicine and animal diseases, reduction of heavy metals, reduction of pollution, water cleanness up to socio-economic issues.

The Czech government imposed strict measures to curb the spread of coronavirus disease at the time that the roundtable was scheduled. Accordingly, the roundtable was organized for the grant holders, JCMM staff and some project supervisors, instead of a more representative and encompassing audience as it was originally planned.

Two of the grant holders during their presentations

During the presentations delegates debated the scientific results, skills improvement and open science activities – students shared their experience in talking to other stakeholders, explaining their project to local municipalities (some cases) and also involving smaller children and explaining them some of the basic scientific principles involved in their projects. Students testified that without the ORION support they would have not be able to execute interesting projects and gain valuable experience. For some of them, it was their first “real” scientific project and they learned important lessons in project management and management of funds. Students also familiarised themselves, some for the first time, with publication processes including the submission of articles to Open Access journals.

Outcomes

Public engagement commitment among scientists

The beneficiaries of this ORION funding coordinated by JCMM took part in the Night of Researchers in September 2019. At that time, they were already in the middle of their projects and were able to share their progress on the achievements of their departments and labs.

Societal interest

The research project focused on pollution in the Moravian Karst was the most far-reaching one. It attracted the interest of a number of stakeholders, the Moravian Karst administration, local majors and state water surveillance authority, prompted two collaborations with schools and was broadcasted on Czech television at prime time. A link of the broadcast: <https://www.ceskatelevize.cz/ivysilani/1097181328-udalosti/220411000100124/obsah/746361-do-jeskyni-v-moravskem-krasu-tece-znecistena-voda>

Another research project that focused on animal hoof diseases and hoof disinfectants attracted the interest of regional animal breeders who sought the groups' advice and offered assistance and their farms for further research.

Open Science leadership

To support the development of this task, JCMM in collaboration with ORION Training Work Package leader, MDC, organized two seminars on Open Science in May 2019. One seminar was for beneficiaries of this ORION funding and another one for other funders in the Brno region. JCMM reckoned that the seminars contributed to recognise JCMM as promoting and leading the Open Science movement in Brno.

JCMM Institutional Changes

A key novel item in this research funding call has been to include an *open public review* in the evaluation process. JCMM uploaded all (anonymised) project proposals in an open online platform ([Authorea](#)) where the public could review and give their feedback. The expert evaluators would then consider the comments of the public during the second round of the evaluation. However, this innovative open public review approach, aligned with the rationale of the ORION project, did not gather much traction. Nevertheless, JCMM intends to improve the approach (by increasing its uptake by the public) to include it where possible in the normal evaluation processes of JCMM funded projects.

JCMM is convinced that the experience will positively influence the future scientific career of the grant holders. Lastly, the expression of interest by representatives in academia for future iterations of this collaborative funding call is another indicator of the impact of this ORION task.

JCMM plans for new call

The positive feedback from the involved parties, i.e. grant holders, their supervisors & universities, motivated JCMM to repeat the call, using the ORION "brand name" & funds from the local government. However, the COVID-19 crisis significantly hampered the plans, as JCMM budget would suffer a significant reduction for the upcoming period(s) and therefore, the plans are currently on hold.

4. Conclusions

This task has provided the two research funding organisations in the ORION consortium with a valuable opportunity to experiment and put in practice open science principles.

First, this task has promoted collaboration, intradepartmental in the case of ISCIII and with local stakeholders in the case of JCOMM. This opportunity to collaborate, which both institutions have recognised and praised, has resulted in **increased institutional permeability** – contributing to improved governance - and national recognition of leadership in Open Science.

Co-creation processes have been at the core of this task. Consulting multiple stakeholders for the development of both approaches to open up research funding in Spain and Czech Republic have been instrumental in the success of this task. The co-creation processes allowed for the development of the task to be divided in smaller phases, more feasible to achieve, and allowed for collective decision-making. They also widened awareness on open science and Responsible Research and Innovation in those countries. The expressed appetite for further iterations of both schemes (the Open Science Funding Call and the RRI Health Awards), points towards the impact of this task and the importance of recognition and rewarding best practices in open science and RRI to support further implementation.

The challenges encountered during the development of the task can be classified in two categories: internal to the partaking organisation and external. The internal challenges are those related to the level of support and resources dedicated to this task. With a task that spans over many months and has several layers of complexity (engagement at the institutional, scientific and stakeholder levels), it is difficult to forecast the level of resourcing it will require. The workload did not require a constant stream of output, which made the task light at times and pressing at other times.

The external challenges are those related to the level of awareness of open science and its practices and stakeholder engagement. Part of the co-creation processes revolved around bringing a level play field of open science understanding among stakeholders. What is it that these complementary approaches seek and why? This was an important message that needed careful consideration by the consortium as well as the participating organisations. Regarding the challenge on stakeholder engagement, this was limited on the one hand by the stakeholders' availability in the given timeframe of the task but also, in the case of the public peer review, by the lack of public awareness and participation in such novel open science process. Due to the novelty of the process, the consortium also encountered lack of awareness about where or how to tap into these target audiences.

Despite the initial challenge that the COVID-19 pandemic instigated to the overall ORION project, this task seemed only slightly affected by this threat and the task leaders swiftly overcame the problems.

Overall, this ORION task has been an excellent exercise to assess weaknesses and strengths on the stakeholder engagement dimension of open science at participating funding organisations. It helped realise that the networks these organisations have are broad and well established and are able to influence national agendas.